

Relevance of transportome among the mechanisms of chemoresistance in hepatoblastoma

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ABSTRACT

Approximately 20 % of hepatoblastomas (HBs) exhibit a poor response to conventional chemotherapy due to mechanisms of chemoresistance (MOCs), such as reduced intracellular drug accumulation. This study evaluated the role of transportome in the multidrug resistance (MDR) of HB. Paired HB and adjacent liver tissue samples (n = 19) and HB-derived cell lines (HepG2, HuH6) were analyzed for their resistome characterization at mRNA (RT-qPCR, Taqman Low-Density Array, sequencing) and protein (western blot, immunohistochemistry, immunofluorescence) levels. Cell viability (MTT test) proliferation and migration (holographic microscopy) were determined. The impact of short-term (72 h) and long-term (>10 months) exposure of HB cells to cisplatin or doxorubicin on the transportome was investigated. Solute carrier (SLC) family of transporters showed minor relevance in HB MDR, while drug export pumps, particularly MRP2, were associated with poor response to chemotherapy. Exposure of HB cells to doxorubicin or cisplatin up-regulated MDR1, MRP1 and MRP2. In cells with induced persistent chemoresistance, the expression of genes involved in other MOCs, and epigenetic machinery was altered. Chemoresistant cells showed cross-resistance to several anticancer drugs but maintained sensitivity to cabozantinib. In conclusion, drug export pumps, but not SLC uptake transporters, are key contributors to HB chemoresistance. Cabozantinib emerges as a potential therapeutic option for HBs resistant to conventional chemotherapy.

Abbreviations: 5-FU, 5-fluorouracil; ABC, ATP-binding cassette; AFP, α -fetoprotein; calcein-AM, calcein acetoxymethyl ester; CF, 5(6)-carboxyfluorescein diacetate; CisPt, cisplatin; CR, cisplatin resistant; Doxo, doxorubicin; DR, doxorubicin resistant; FBS, fetal bovine serum; FTC, fumitremorgin C; HB, hepatoblastoma; HCC, hepatocellular carcinoma; IC₅₀, half-maximal inhibitory concentration; IF, immunofluorescence; IHC, immunohistochemistry; IQR, interquartile range; MDR, multidrug resistance; MOC, mechanism of chemoresistance; N.D., not detected; NR, non-responder; NT, non-tumor tissue; OS, overall survival; PRETEXT, PRE-Treatment and EXTension of the tumor; qPCR, quantitative PCR; R, responder; ROC, receiver operating characteristic; RNA-seq, RNA sequencing; RT, reverse transcription; SLC, solute carrier; TKI, tyrosine kinase inhibitor; TLDA, Taqman Low-Density Array; WT, wild type.

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1. Introduction

Hepatoblastoma (HB) is the most common liver cancer in children. In contrast to hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), which generally affects adults with underlying cirrhosis, HB develops in the absence of apparent liver disease [1]. Although rare, with an incidence of approximately two cases per million children, its occurrence has risen globally at a rate higher than that of other pediatric cancers in recent decades [2]. Most cases are diagnosed within the first three years of life [3], typically through physical examination, elevated α -1-fetoprotein (AFP) levels (present in ≈ 90 % of cases) [3], imaging studies, and histological analysis. Histopathologically, HB reflects different stages of liver development [4]. Well-differentiated fetal HBs have an epithelial phenotype, whereas immature forms such as embryonal component usually display aggressive behavior, metastasis, and chemoresistance [2,5].

Genomic, transcriptomic, epigenetic and metabolomic analyses have facilitated the molecular classifications of HB. Cairo *et al.* [5] identified two subtypes of this liver cancer (C1, C2) based on the expression profile of 16 genes, with C1 linked to mature hepatocyte markers and C2 to liver progenitor cell markers. Hooks *et al.* [6] further divided C2 into two subgroups C2A and C2B, differing in the expression of four genes (*HSD17B6*, *ITGA6*, *TOP2A*, and *VIM*). Recent epigenetic studies proposed two clusters, Epi-CA and Epi-CB, based on DNA methylation profiles and an integrative molecular risk stratification of HB [7].

Clinically, HB is stratified using CHIC stratification [8] that is based on the PRETEXT (from PRETreatment and EXTension of the tumor) algorithm, which assesses tumor extension (I-IV) to guide personalized therapeutic strategies [9]. Treatment options include: chemotherapy (neoadjuvant/adjuvant), surgical resection, and liver transplantation [10]. Although most patients with HB respond to standard pharmacological treatment, based mainly on a combination of doxorubicin and cisplatin [11], ≈ 20 % of patients exhibit aggressive, chemoresistant tumors with poor prognosis [12,13], and ≈ 12 % of patients initially considered in complete remission are prone to relapse [14]. Additional prognostic factors included in the CHIC stratification are age at diagnosis, serum levels of AFP, PRETEXT stage, and the presence of metastases. Molecular features, such as C2-pure subtype and epigenetic alterations (Epi-CB subtypes), are also associated with worse outcomes [15].

The lack of response of HB to pharmacological treatment involves complex mechanisms of chemoresistance (MOCs), which can be inherently present in HB cells or develop after exposure to antitumor drugs, conferring multidrug resistance (MDR). MOCs have been classified into seven groups depending on whether they account for: a reduction in the intracellular drug content, thereby limiting its ability to reach its target, which can result from decreased expression or function of plasma membrane solute carriers (SLCs) responsible for drug uptake (MOC-1a) or from increased expression of ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters involved in drug export (MOC-1b). Additionally, a lower proportion of active drug within tumor cells may arise due to alterations in drug-metabolizing enzymes, either through reduced expression of those involved in pro-drug activation or increased expression of inactivating enzymes (MOC-2). Chemoresistance can also occur due to modifications in the expression or function of molecular targets (MOC-3); enhanced DNA repair mechanisms counteracting drug-induced damage (MOC-4), and dysregulated apoptotic pathways (MOC-5), either via reduced pro-apoptotic factors (MOC-5a) or up-regulated pro-survival genes (MOC-5b). Further contributing factors include alterations in the tumor microenvironment (MOC-6) and phenotypic transformations, such as epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) or the acquisition of stemness characteristics (MOC-7) [16]. Changes in the expression levels of genes accounting for these MOCs, the so-called resistome, and the presence of genetic variants in these genes can influence drug response and, hence, patient outcomes [16,17]. This study aimed to characterize the HB resistome, with a focus on the transportome (accounting for MOC-1) and

to evaluate the impact of chemotherapy on gene expression. Additionally, the existence of cross-resistance and the identification of collateral drug sensitivity were investigated in chemoresistant HB cell models developed for this purpose.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Human samples

Samples from surgically resected HBs and paired adjacent nontumor tissue ($n = 19$) were obtained from the Childhood Liver Oncology Group at the Germans Trias i Pujol Research Institute (IGTP) in Badalona, Spain. The study was conducted in compliance with national regulations, and the protocol received approval from the Ethics Committees for Clinical Research of IGTP and Salamanca University Hospital (Ref. 2020-02-42). To utilize biological samples in biomedical research, written informed consent was obtained from patients or their legally authorized representatives. Relevant clinical and pathological information is summarized in Table 1. All patients received neoadjuvant chemotherapy, and the reduction in serum AFP levels served as a surrogate marker for chemotherapy response. Patients were categorized as responders (R) when the percentage of reduction of AFP values after treatment was ≥ 90 %, while those with a lower percentage were classified as non-responders (NR).

2.2. Chemicals

5(6)-carboxyfluorescein diacetate (CF), cisplatin, diclofenac, doxorubicin, epirubicin, etoposide, 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), fumitremorgin C (FTC), irinotecan, mitoxantrone, probenecid, rhodamine 123, verapamil, vinblastine, and vincristine were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck, Madrid). Calcein acetoxymethyl ester (calcein-AM) was purchased from Invitrogen (Thermo Fisher, Madrid). Oxaliplatin was obtained from Acros Organics (Thermo Fisher). Cabozantinib, idarubicin, lenvatinib, PFI-2, regorafenib, and sorafenib were acquired from Selleckchem (Deltaclon, Madrid). All chemicals were of ≥ 98 % purity. CM-272, a dual inhibitor of G9a and DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) activity, was synthesized as previously published [18].

2.3. Cell cultures

Human HB cell lines HepG2 (HB-8065) and HuH6 cells (JCRB0401) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) (LGC Standards, Barcelona, Spain) or the Japanese Collection of Research Bioresources Cell Bank (Osaka, Japan), respectively. HepG2 cells were cultured in MEM medium (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS, 10 %), penicillin/streptomycin/amphotericin B (Thermo Fisher), 1 mM sodium pyruvate (Sigma-Aldrich), and 26 mM sodium bicarbonate (Sigma-Aldrich). HuH6 cells were cultured in DMEM medium (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with FBS (10 %), penicillin, streptomycin (Thermo Fisher), and GlutaMAX (Thermo Fisher) (passages 15–40).

Drug resistant sublines (HuH6/CR for cisplatin resistance and HepG2/DR for doxorubicin resistance) were developed by exposing wild type (WT) cells to increasing drug concentrations over 10 months; from 0.1 to 2 μ M cisplatin and from 10 to 200 nM doxorubicin. Cell morphology, viability, and growth rate were monitored during resistance development. Resistant cells were maintained in drug-containing culture media unless stated otherwise (passages 40–80). Cell lines were verified to be mycoplasma-free throughout the experiments using the Mycoplasma Gel Form Kit (Biotools B&M Labs, Madrid).

2.4. Determination of cell viability and cell proliferation rate

To determine cytostatic activity, 7,500 cells/well (HepG2-WT and HepG2/DR), 4,000 cells/well (HuH6), and 8,000 cells/well (HuH6/CR)

Table 1
Clinical and pathologic characteristics of HB patients.

Characteristics	Values
Age, months (mean/range)	14.5/3.8–65
Sex (Male/Female)	11/8
Serum AFP, ng/mL (range)	18,000–2,186,461
Histology (Epithelial/Fetal/Mixed/Full regression)	6/1/11/1
Molecular subclass (C1/C2)	9/10
Tumor stage	
PRETEXT stage (I/II/III/IV)	1/7/7/4
Metastasis at diagnosis (Y/N)	3/16
Multifocality (Y/N)	6/13
Vascular invasion (Y/N)	4/15
Pre-surgical chemotherapy (Y/N)	19/0
Response to chemotherapy (Y/N)	14/5
SIOPEL protocol (3/4/6)	5/5/9
Follow-up, months (mean/range)	47.1/3.5–96.5
Dead of the disease	5 %

AFP, alpha-fetoprotein; PRETEXT, pretreatment extent of disease; Y/N, Yes/No.

were seeded in 96-well plates. After 24 h, cells were exposed to several concentrations of compounds for 72 h. Cell viability was measured using MTT-formazan or sulforhodamine B assays, as previously reported [19], and proliferation rates were assessed via real-time digital holographic cytometry with a HoloMonitor® Live Cell Imaging System (Phase Holographic Imaging PHI AB, Lund, Sweden).

2.5. Clonogenic and cell migration assays

Cell migration was analyzed using wound healing assays. Monolayer wounds were captured at various time points using phase holographic microscopy. Colony formation assays were performed by seeding 1000 cells per well into 6-well plates and culturing them for 15 days (HepG2) or 10 days (HuH-6), with media changes every 2–3 days. Colonies were fixed for 5 min using a methanol: acetic acid solution (7:1 ratio) at room temperature and stained with 0.05 % crystal violet in 25 % methanol for 15 min. After washing with water to remove the excess of crystal violet, colonies were counted, and their area was calculated using ImageJ imaging software (NIH, MD, USA).

2.6. Transport assays

Cells in suspension were incubated at 37 °C for 30 min in 100 µl of “transport buffer” (96 mM NaCl, 5.3 mM KCl, 0.8 mM MgSO₄, 1.1 mM KH₂PO₄, 1.8 mM CaCl₂, 11 mM glucose, and 50 mM HEPES, pH 7.40 adjusted with Tris) containing fluorescent substrates of ABC proteins: rhodamine 123 for MDR1, calcein-AM for MRP1 and MRP2, CF for MRP3, MRP4, and MRP5, and mitoxantrone for BCRP. This loading period was terminated by diluting with 900 µl of substrate-free medium, with or without transporter inhibitors (verapamil for MDR1, probenecid for MRP1 and MRP2, diclofenac for MRP3, MRP4, and MRP5, and FTC for BCRP), and intracellular fluorescence was determined by flow cytometry in a FACSCalibur flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, Madrid). Efflux of the preloaded substrate occurred in the diluted medium before measuring the intracellular substrate content again. The export activity of ABC proteins was determined by calculating the difference in intracellular content between the end of the loading phase (30 min) and the completion of the efflux phase (30 min). Efflux was quantified as the percentage of the total substrate initially loaded.

2.7. Quantification of gene expression

Total RNA was isolated using RNA mini-spin columns treated with RNase-free DNase I with the illustraRNAspin Mini RNA Isolation Kit (GE Healthcare, Madrid). Reverse transcription (RT) was performed using random primers and SuperScript VILO cDNA Synthesis kit (Invitrogen) or High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription kit (Applied Biosystems,

Thermo Fisher).

Quantitative PCR (qPCR) was conducted using gene-specific primers spanning exon-exon junctions in the target mRNA (Table 2). Reactions were performed in single-tube assays with AmpliTaq Gold DNA polymerase and the SYBR Green I detection kit on a QuantStudio™ 3 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems) or using Taqman Low-Density Arrays (TLDA) in an ABI Prism 7900HT Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems). Thermal cycling conditions were the following: single cycles at 50 °C for 2 min and at 95 °C for 10 min, and 40 cycles at 95 °C for 15 s and at 60 °C for 60 s. The mRNA abundance was normalized based on *ROTH2* content for single-tube qPCR, while *ACTB* was used for TLDA analyses. 18S rRNA was used as a quality control check.

2.8. Determination of gene expression by high-throughput techniques

RNA sequencing (RNA-Seq) in cell lines was performed at the University of Salamanca Sequencing Service. After checking the integrity of the RNA using the TapeStation bioanalyser (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara CA), mRNA libraries were prepared using 1 µg of total RNA and the ‘mRNA HyperPrep-Kit.Illumina’ method (Roche, Basel, Switzerland), according to the manufacturer’s specifications. Sequencing was performed on a NovaSeq 6000 configured with 2x100bp and 50 M paired end reads. RNA-Seq data was analyzed by the University of Salamanca’s Bioinformatics Unit through the alignment of reads and quantification of gene expression using DEXSeq and EdgeR methods for exon counting.

High-throughput proteomic analyses of cell lysates were conducted using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) on a timsTOF Pro with PASEF instrument (Bruker Daltonics) coupled online to an Evosep ONE. A total of 200 ng of sample was directly loaded onto an analytical column (EVOSEP) and separated at a flow rate of 300 nL/min using a 44-minute gradient. Protein identification and quantification were performed with PEAKS X software (Bioinformatics Solutions). Peptide quantity normalization and batch effect correction were carried out using the proBatch R package.

2.9. Immunoblotting and immunofluorescence assays

Immunoblotting analyses of cell lysates, prepared in RIPA buffer, were performed using 7.5–10 % SDS-PAGE gels loading twenty to fifty µg of protein homogenate per lane. In some cases, samples were denatured by heating at 100 °C for 5 min. Subsequently, proteins were transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes. Blots were probed with primary antibodies (Table 3). Appropriate horseradish peroxidase-linked secondary antibodies (Invitrogen) were diluted 1:2000. An enhanced chemiluminescence detection system (Hybond ECL; GE Healthcare) was used for band visualization in a LAS-4000 image analysis system (Fujifilm, TDI, Madrid).

Immunofluorescence (IF) staining was performed on cells cultured on coverslips, which were fixed and permeabilized with ice-cold methanol or, in the case of BCRP, with 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) followed by 0.1 % Triton-X. The cells were subsequently incubated with primary antibodies (Table 3). The secondary antibodies conjugated to Alexa Fluor-488 or Alexa Fluor-594 (Thermo Fisher) were diluted at a 1:2000 ratio. Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI (Sigma-Aldrich). Confocal laser-scanning microscopy was performed using a Leica TCS SP2 confocal microscope.

Immunohistochemistry (IHC) was carried out at the Pathology Service of the Salamanca University Hospital Complex using formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) sections from eight HBs. The process included antigen retrieval at pH 6.0 and incubation with primary antibodies (Table 3) for 40 min in a Leica Biosystems BOND-III Fully Automated IHC and ISH Stainer. Slides were counterstained with hematoxylin (Palex, Madrid) and mounted using an aqueous mounting medium. Imaging was performed at ×200 magnification using the dot-Slide virtual image system (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) at the Comparative

Table 2

Forward (F) and reverse (R) primers used to determine the expression levels of the genes of interest by RT-qPCR.

Gene	Protein	Primers	Type	Amplicon (bp)	Accesion number
<i>ABCB1</i>	MDR1	GCGCGAGGTCGGAAATGGAT	F	198	NM_000927
		CCATGGATGATGGCAGCCAAAGTT	R		
<i>ABCC1</i>	MRP1	CGCTCTGGGACTGGAAATGT	F	215	NM_004996
		GTGTCATCTGAATGTAGCCTCGGT	R		
<i>ABCC2</i>	MRP2	TGAAGAGGAAGCCACAGTCCATGA	F	171	NM_000392
		TTCAGATGCCTGCCATTGGACCTA	R		
<i>ABCC3</i>	MRP3	CCAAGTTCTGGGACTCCAACCTG	F	160	NM_003786
		ATGATGTAGCCACGACAATGGTGC	R		
<i>ABCC4</i>	MRP4	TGCAAGGGTTCTGGGATAAAGA	F	141	NM_005845
		CTTTGGCACTTCTCCTCAATTAACG	R		
<i>ABCC5</i>	MRP5	CGTGAACTGCAGAAGACTAGAGAGACT	F	128	NM_005688
		GGCACACGATGGACAGGATGA	R		
<i>ABCG2</i>	BCRP	CCGAGGCCTCTATAGCTCAGATCATT	F	161	NM_004827
		CACGGCTGAAACACTGTGAAACA	R		
<i>RHOT2</i>	RHOT2	CTGCGGACTATCTCTCCCTC	F	151	NM_138769
		AAAAGGCTTTGCAGCTCCAC	R		
<i>SLC22A1</i>	OCT1	TGCAGACAGGTTTGCCCT	F	187	NM_003057
		GCCCAGCCAACAAATCTGTGAT	R		
<i>SLC22A3</i>	OCT3	CATCGTCACGAGTTTGACCTTGT	F	139	NM_021977
		GTAATGAGGATCCTGCCATACCTGTCT	R		
<i>SLC31A1</i>	CTR1	GGAAATCTTGCCCACTAAACCCAG	F	277	NM_001859
		TCCGCCTCTAGGTTCAAGTGATT	R		
<i>SLCO1B1</i>	OATP1B1	GCATCACCTGAGATAGTGGAAAAGGTT	F	104	NM_006446
		GGAGTCTCCCTATTCACGAAGCATAT	R		
<i>SLCO1B3</i>	OATP1B3	GATTCAAGATGTTCTTGGCAGCCCT	F	136	NM_019844
		CCATCAATTAACCCAGCAAGAGAAGAGGA	R		
<i>SLCO2B1</i>	OATP2B1	GAAGGGCAAGGACTCTCCCTCTA	F	87	NM_007256
		GTCAGGTTTGGTGAATCTGGACT	R		

bp, base pairs; F, forward; R, reverse.

Molecular Pathology Unit of Salamanca Centro de Investigación del Cáncer. Images were acquired using Olympus software (DotSlide, OLYM, Olympus).

2.10. Statistical analysis

Data processing and statistical analyses were performed using Microsoft Office Excel (version 365) and GraphPad Prism 8. For normally distributed data, results were expressed as mean \pm SEM, and statistical significance between groups was assessed using parametric tests. Student's *t*-tests were applied for comparisons between two sample groups, with paired or unpaired tests used as appropriate. For non-normally distributed data, results were presented as median and interquartile range (IQR), and the statistical significance of the differences between groups was determined using nonparametric tests. Specifically, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were employed for paired samples, while Mann-Whitney *U* tests were used for unpaired comparisons. The performance of transportome gene expression in predicting HB patients' response, encompassing accuracy, sensitivity and specificity, was assessed through binormal Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves using online software (<https://www.rad.jhmi.edu/jeng/javara/d/roc/JROCFITi.html>) from Johns Hopkins University School of Medicine, MD, US.

3. Results

3.1. Transportome characterization in HB clinical samples

In this study, we focused on transporters involved in the uptake and efflux of drugs used in HB. Specifically, we explored the role of drug uptake transporters OATP1B1, OATP1B3, OATP2B1, OCT1, OCT3 and CTR1 (*SLCO1B1*, *SLCO1B3*, *SLCO2B1*, *SLC22A1*, *SLC22A3* and *SLC31A1* genes, respectively), and drug efflux pumps MDR1, MRP1-5 and BCRP (*ABCB1*, *ABCC1-5* and *ABCG2* genes, respectively). mRNA expression was quantified by RT-qPCR in 19 paired samples of HB and adjacent nontumor tissue (NT) samples (Fig. 1). *RHOT2* served as a normalizer

due to its consistent expression in HB. Patients included in this cohort had received cisplatin and doxorubicin-based chemotherapy before sample collection. Table 1 presents the clinical and pathological characteristics of patients.

The expression levels of all uptake transporters, except for *SLC22A3*, were lower in HB than in NT. Among these genes, *SLCO1B3* and *SLC22A1* exhibited the lowest mRNA expression in HB (Fig. 1A). The remaining transporters showed moderate to high expression levels in HB. All analyzed pumps were highly expressed in HB (Fig. 1B), which supports their potential role in chemoresistance, despite some differences with NT were found. Thus, compared to NT, there was a significant increase in mRNA levels of *ABCC5* and a trend in those of *ABCC1* and *ABCC4* in HB, while *ABCB1*, *ABCC2*, and *ABCG2* were downregulated.

Regarding HB subtypes, the expression levels of *SLCO1B1*, *SLCO2B1*, and *SLC22A1* were significantly lower in C2 tumors compared to C1 tumors (Fig. 1A). However, no significant differences were observed in export pumps (Fig. 1B). Regarding treatment response, no significant differences in any uptake transporter between responders (R) and non-responders (NR) were found, and only a trend toward lower expression of *SLC22A1* in NR was seen (Fig. 1A). However, the expression of the export pumps was significantly higher in NR (Fig. 1B).

Next, we analyzed the relationship between changes in the transportome and the lack of response to chemotherapy, indirectly measured by decreased serum AFP levels following pharmacological treatment. Considering the low expression of uptake transporters and high expression of drug export pumps as predictors of chemoresistance, *SLC22A1* (Fig. 2A) and *ABCC2* (Fig. 2B) exhibited the highest values of specificity (71.4 and 85.7 %, respectively) and sensitivity (57.1 and 78.6 %, respectively), while the other transporters showed poor values (Fig. 2C). Although OCT1 transports doxorubicin and cisplatin, this transporter was not further investigated due to low expression in most tumors.

Concerning transport proteins, besides expression levels, their correct function requires their localization in the plasma membrane of tumor cells; we performed an IHC analysis of the most relevant

Table 3

Primary antibodies and conditions used for protein detection by Western blot, immunofluorescence or immunohistochemistry.

Antigen	Host	Manufacturer	Catalog#	Dilution
Western blot				
MDR1	Mouse	Thermo Fisher	C219	1:1000
MRP1	Rat	Enzo Life Sciences	MRPr1	1:500
MRP2	Mouse	Enzo Life Sciences	M2III6	1:1000
MRP3	Rabbit	Sigma-Aldrich	M0318	1:500
MRP4	Rat	Abcam	M4I-10	1:1000
MRP5	Rat	OriGene	M5I-10	1:50
BCRP	Mouse	Abcam	BXP-21	1:500
α -tubulin	Mouse	Sigma-Aldrich	DM1A	1:1000
Immunofluorescence				
MDR1	Mouse	Thermo Fisher	C219	1:25
MRP1	Rat	Enzo Life Sciences	MRPr1	1:40
MRP2	Mouse	Enzo Life Sciences	M2III6	1:33
MRP3	Mouse	Abcam	M3III9	1:50
MRP4	Goat	Novus	NB100-1471	1:50
MRP5	Rat	OriGene	M5I-10	1:25
BCRP	Mouse	Abcam	BXP-21	1:50
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase	Mouse	Abcam	M7-PB-E9	1:100
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase	Rabbit	Abcam	EP1845Y	1:100
Immunohistochemistry				
MDR1	Rabbit	Cell Signaling	E1Y7B	1:50
MRP1	Mouse	Santa Cruz	QCRL-1	1:50
MRP2	Mouse	Enzo	M2III-5	1:25

transporter in HB chemoresistance based on the results described above, specifically MRP2 in eight paired tumor and non-tumor samples, four from the R group and four from the NR group. For comparison, we also analyzed MDR1 and MRP1. As expected, MDR1 and MRP2 were localized in the canalicular membrane of the hepatocytes and in the apical plasma membrane of cholangiocytes. We also found intracellular labeling for MRP1 in hepatocytes and cholangiocytes as it is less expressed and typically localized in the basolateral membrane of hepatocytes (Fig. 3A-D). Considerable inter-individual variability was found in IHC analysis results of HB samples. Here, we present representative images of a tumor included in the responder group (R) with low MDR1, MRP1, and MRP2 staining (Fig. 3E-H), together with another one included in the non-responder group (NR), with high staining of these pumps (Fig. 3I-L).

3.2. Modulation of the transportome in HB cells following short-term exposure to antitumor drugs

Since the samples included in the study were from previously treated children, it was not possible to characterize the transportome profile in naïve patients nor investigate the effect of drug exposure. As an alternative, we used *in vitro* models, specifically, HB-derived cells HepG2 and HuH6. Dose-response curves for the cytotoxic effects of cisplatin and doxorubicin revealed a similar pattern for both cell lines (data not shown). We conducted a short-term exposure (72 h) of HepG2 and HuH6 to cisplatin and doxorubicin at near their half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀, 5 μ M and 0.1 μ M, respectively) to evaluate transportome changes (Figs. 4 and 5). Uptake transporters (Fig. 4) were expressed at negligible levels (*SLCO1B1*, and *SLCO1B3* in both cell lines, and *SLC22A3* in HuH6 cells), or showed very low expression (*SLC22A1* in HuH6 cells). Short-term exposure to doxorubicin or cisplatin had no significant effect on the mRNA levels of uptake transporters in HepG2 cells (Fig. 4A). In HuH6 cells, a modest up-regulation was observed in response to pharmacological stress (Fig. 4B), which would not be consistent with decreased sensitivity.

In contrast, both drugs significantly up-regulated efflux transporters in HepG2 (Fig. 5A) and HuH6 (Fig. 5D) cells, with the exception of *ABCC4* and *ABCC5*. Western blot analysis (Fig. 5B and 5E) and functional assays (Fig. 5C and 5F) confirmed these findings, although the functional changes were less pronounced.

3.3. Generation of chemoresistant HB cells

HB cells with persistent resistance to either doxorubicin or cisplatin were established by exposing HepG2 and HuH6 cells to stepwise increasing concentrations of each drug for at least 10 months. After this selection process, HepG2 cells tolerant to 200 nM doxorubicin (HepG2/DR) (Fig. 6A), and HuH6 cells capable of growing in the presence of 2 μ M cisplatin (HuH6/CR) (Fig. 6B) were obtained. Accordingly, the IC₅₀ values for chemoresistant cells were markedly increased (4-fold and 50-fold, respectively) compared to their parental wild-type cells. Interestingly, the resistance persisted even after removing the pharmacological pressure (DR- and CR-, respectively). The sensitivity of HepG2/DR cells to doxorubicin remained unchanged 10 days after being cultured in the absence of this drug, showing minimal recovery after an additional 18-day period. The sensitivity of HuH6/CR cells to cisplatin persisted for at least 28 of culturing the cells with the cisplatin-free medium.

Besides chemoresistance, other characteristics of malignancy were observed in the generated cells. Thus, cell proliferation rate was slower in HepG2-DR than in wild-type HepG2 cells. This difference was not abolished by culturing the chemoresistant cells in the absence of doxorubicin for up to 28 days (Fig. 7A). Cell migration, as determined by the wound-healing test, was also slower in HepG2-DR cells (Fig. 7A). Moreover, these cells formed fewer and smaller colonies than their parental wild-type cells (Fig. 7A). Similar phenotypic changes were seen in HuH6-CR cells. Besides slower cell proliferation and cell migration (Fig. 7B), the colony formation was also less efficient in HuH6-CR cells as compared with wild-type HuH6 cells (Fig. 7B).

3.4. Changes in the resistome of chemoresistant HB cells

To characterize the resistome of chemoresistant cells, the expression of a panel of 93 MOC genes was determined by RT-qPCR using TLDAs (Fig. 8). Regarding drug transporters (MOC-1), some genes involved in drug uptake, such as *SLC29A2*, *SLC47A1*, and *SLCO4A1*, showed lower expression in HepG2/DR cells (Fig. 8A). In contrast, a marked increase in the expression of the drug export pump *ABCB1* was found. Other genes encoding doxorubicin exporters, such as *ABCC1* and *ABCC2*, were moderately up-regulated. Moreover, some enzymes that participate in drug metabolism were down-regulated, while others had higher expression in HepG2/DR cells (MOC-2). In the MOC-3 group, we found that doxorubicin target *TOP2A* was down-regulated in resistant cells. Several genes involved in DNA repair processes (MOC-4) were up-regulated in HepG2-DR cells; *ERCC1*, *MLH1*, and *PMS1* stood out among them. Among pro-apoptotic genes (MOC-5a), only *PTEN*, which was already poorly expressed in wild-type HepG2 cells, was down-regulated in HepG2/DR cells. In contrast, several genes favoring cell survival (MOC-5b) were up-regulated in chemoresistant cells. No change in MOC-6 genes associated with changes in tumor microenvironment was found. Interestingly, an increased expression of several genes involved in the acquisition of stem cell characteristics (MOC-7) was seen.

Changes in the transportome of HuH6/CR cells were also detected (Fig. 8B). These were down-regulation of nucleoside uptake transporters (mainly *SLC29A2*) (MOC-1a) and up-regulation of several export pumps (MOC-1b), including *ABCB1* and *ABCC2*. The up-regulation of some drug-metabolizing enzymes (MOC-2) was found in chemoresistant cells. Regarding changes in molecular targets (MOC-3), marked up-regulations (e.g., *TOP2A*) and down-regulations (e.g., *PDGFRA*) were observed in chemoresistant cells. Genes involved in DNA repair processes (MOC-4), which are particularly relevant in resistance to cisplatin

Fig. 1. Relative mRNA levels of drug uptake transporters (A) and drug export pumps (B) in paired samples ($n = 19$) of hepatoblastoma (HB) tumor (T) and adjacent non-tumor tissue (NT) measured by RT-qPCR. Squares are mean \pm SEM. *, $p < 0.05$, compared with NT tissue using the Wilcoxon test for paired samples. The above values of gene expression were classified into two groups of HB defined by a 16-gene signature (C1 or C2). Alternatively, the tumors were classified into those that responded (R) or did not respond (NR) to standard chemotherapy as determined by the reduction of serum alpha-fetoprotein levels. Values are shown as the median and IQR of individual data points (circles). *, $p < 0.05$, comparing C1 ($n = 9$) vs. C2 ($n = 10$) tumors or R ($n = 14$) vs. NR ($n = 5$) tumors using the Mann-Whitney U test.

Fig. 2. Maximum likelihood estimation of binormal receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve to validate the *SLC22A1* (A) or *ABCC2* (B) expression performance in predicting response of hepatoblastoma (HB) patients to chemotherapy. Analysis of ROC curves evaluating the predictive capacity of drug uptake and efflux transporter expression in tumors for the response of HB patients to chemotherapy (C). Patients ($n = 19$) were categorized as responders or non-responders based on standard clinical criteria, defining a positive response as achieving a $>90\%$ reduction in serum alpha-fetoprotein values post-treatment.

due to the mechanism of action of this drug, were up-regulated in HuH6/CR cells (e.g., *ERCC1*). Regarding genes involved in activating apoptosis (MOC-5a) or promoting cell survival (MOC-5a) marked down-regulation and up-regulation, respectively, of relevant genes were not found. The expression of genes associated with chemoresistance due to changes in tumor microenvironment (MOC-6) was not altered in chemoresistant cells. Among genes that promote the acquisition of stem cell characteristics (MOC-7), the expression of *ALDH1A1*, *CD44* and *TGFB1* was significantly increased in HuH6/CR cells.

Given the focus of the present study on the role of ABC export pumps in HB chemoresistance, the subcellular localization of these transporters in chemoresistant cells was analyzed by IF (Fig. 9). In HepG2/DR cells, MDR1, MRP1, and MRP4 were mainly located in the plasma membrane, while MRP2 and MRP5 were mostly intracellular. In contrast, in HuH6/CR cells, MRP1, MRP4, MRP5, and BCRP were mainly found in the plasma membrane, whereas MRP2-associated signals were intracellular, and MDR1 was not detected.

The results obtained by qPCR were compared with those obtained in HepG2 (WT vs. DR) and HuH6 (WT vs. CR) cells by RNA-Seq and high-throughput proteomics (Table 4). The three techniques used revealed some similarities and discrepancies, as well as differences and shared changes between cell lines.

3.5. Changes in the expression of epigenetic genes in chemoresistant HB cells

Given the relevance of impaired epigenetic control in HB biology, the expression of profile of more than 400 genes involved in this process (erasers, readers, scaffolds, and writers) was analyzed by RNA-Seq. This study revealed differential expression of several genes in chemoresistant cells compared with their wild-type counterparts (Table 5). While some changes were observed in both cell lines (e.g., *PRDM7* up-regulation), others showed opposite patterns (e.g., *HR* was down-regulated in HepG2/DR cells but up-regulated in HuH6/CR cells). Moreover, the

Fig. 3. Representative images of histological sections of adjacent non-tumor infant liver tissue (A-D) and two selected hepatoblastoma (HB) tumors, one with good response to chemotherapy (HB-R) and one with poor response to chemotherapy (HB-NR), stained with hematoxylin-eosin (A, E, I) or after immunohistochemical staining for MDR1 (B, F, J), MRP1 (C, G, K) or MRP2 (D, H, L). In all the cases, slides were counterstained with hematoxylin. Arrows point canalicular expression (3B and 3D). Scale bar: 50 μ m.

expression of several other genes was significantly altered in only one cell line. Specifically, *HDAC*, *UTY*, *CHD5*, *PAX6*, *SFMBT2*, *EID1*, *MECOM*, *PRDM6*, *PRDM8*, *RAG1* and *SETD7* were significantly up-regulated in HepG2/DR compared to HepG2/WT. Among the genes differentially expressed in HuH6/CR versus HuH6/WT, *PADI2*, *PHF19*, *NAIP1L2*, *SNAI2*, and *PARP10* were up-regulated, while *USP44*, *MLLT3*, and *PDP1* were down-regulated.

3.6. Evaluation of cross-resistance and lateral sensitivity in chemoresistant HB cells

As a final step of the characterization of chemoresistant cells we investigated the existence of cross-resistance to other antitumor drugs commonly used to treat this cancer (Fig. 10). The results revealed that, in general, HepG2/DR and HuH6/CR cells were more resistant to anthracyclines, and etoposide than their wild-type counterparts. Interestingly, we found cross-resistance to cisplatin in HepG2/DR cells and to doxorubicin in HuH6/CR cells. In contrast, no cross-resistance against 5-FU and *Vinca* alkaloids was seen (Fig. 10, Table 6). While HepG2/DR cells showed no cross-resistance to any tested TKIs used to treat HCC, HuH6/CR were resistant to sorafenib, regorafenib, and lenvatinib. Interestingly, the response to cabozantinib was unaltered in both chemoresistant cells.

Besides, as an attempt to modulate chemoresistance, based on results of marked impact of chemoresistance in the expression of epigenetic genes, we evaluated the effect of inhibitors of epigenetic factors such CM-272, able to inhibit histone methyltransferase G9a [20], and lysine methyltransferase SETD7 (PFI-2) [21] in the response of HB cells to doxorubicin and cisplatin. In both HepG2 (Fig. 10A) and HuH6 (Fig. 10B) cells, either sensitive or resistant to these drugs, the treatment with CM-272 and PFI-2 for 72 h did not induce enhanced cytotoxic response.

4. Discussion

Since it is well recognized that changes in the expression and

function of drug transport proteins have an important impact on the chemoresistance of major liver and gastrointestinal tumors in adults [22], but their contribution to the MDR phenotype of HB has been less explored, this study addresses this gap by characterizing the expression of drug uptake and export transporters in HB clinical samples from patients who had received cisplatin and doxorubicin prior undergoing surgery. Most uptake transporters were downregulated in HB tissue in comparison with paired surrounding NT tissue. Similar findings were previously reported in a small number of untreated patient samples for the organic cation transporter OCT1 (gene *SLC22A1*) [23], which can transport doxorubicin and has been associated with poor response of patients with HCC and cholangiocarcinoma to several anticancer drugs [24,25]. Moreover, the low expression of functional variants of other drug uptake transporters has been related to weak response to chemotherapy [26]. Regarding ABC drug export pumps, *ABCC5* expression was higher in HB than in NT. MRP5 is involved in the resistance to anthracyclines [27] and cisplatin [28]. There is also a trend for MRP1 (*ABCC1* gene) expression to be elevated in HB. Although high levels of both pumps have been associated with poor prognosis in other solid tumors, such as MRP1 in neuroblastoma [29] and MRP5 in metastatic colorectal cancer [30], in our cohort of HB patients, both genes showed low sensitivity values as predictive markers of treatment response. The expression of other ABC pumps involved in doxorubicin and cisplatin efflux, such as *ABCB1*, *ABCC2*, and *ABCG2* was elevated in HB but, surprisingly, lower than that in NT tissue. Other authors reported an increased expression of MDR1, MRP1 and BCRP in HB after being treated with cisplatin and doxorubicin, and no changes in MRP2 [31–33], while BCRP down-regulation has been reported in other tumors treated with platinum derivatives [34].

The high expression of MRP2 in tumors with poor responses to cisplatin [35,36] and doxorubicin [37] suggests that this transporter may be a prognostic marker in HB upon IHC analysis. This would determine whether the protein is expressed and well localized in the plasma membrane, as has been reported in HCC [25].

Besides intrinsic resistance mechanisms already present in naïve cancer cells, the resistome is modified upon exposure to antitumor

Fig. 4. Effect of short-term exposure of HepG2 (A) and HuH6 (B) cells to doxorubicin or cisplatin on the expression of drug uptake transporters. Cells were cultured in the absence (Control) or presence of either 0.1 μM doxorubicin (+Doxo) or 5 μM cisplatin (+CisPt) (close to their IC_{50}) for 72 h. Relative expression was determined by RT-qPCR as mRNA levels as the percentage of those of the housekeeping gene, *RHO2*. Values are mean \pm SEM of 3 independent experiments performed in duplicate wells. *, $p < 0.05$, compared to Control by paired *t*-test.

agents [38]. Considering the ethical limitation to investigate this process by collecting HB samples before and after the treatment, two *in vitro* approaches were used to simulate the impact on the resistome, and more specifically on the transportome, upon acute and long-term exposure to chemotherapy. The most relevant finding was the up-regulation of drug export pumps, such as MDR1, MRP1 MRP2 and MRP5, whose association with the lack of response to anthracyclines has been previously described in liver cancers [22,39], including HB [32,40].

Besides changes in the transportome (MOC-1), chemoresistant cells

also showed differential expression in genes involved in other MOCs, such as up-regulation of enzymes involved in phase II of drug metabolism, like GSTs, which has been associated with resistance to doxorubicin and cisplatin [41,42]. Alterations in the expression of doxorubicin's target topoisomerase II could also contribute to the lack of response to this anthracycline [16,43], whereas changes in genes involved in DNA repair are particularly important in cisplatin resistance [16,44]. Moreover, in our investigation of chemoresistant cells we also found alterations in the epigenetic machinery, such as SETD7 up-

Fig. 5. Effect of exposure of HepG2 (A) and HuH6 (D) cells to doxorubicin or cisplatin on the expression of different drug efflux transporters. Cells were cultured in the absence (Control) or presence of either 0.1 μ M doxorubicin (+Doxo) or 5 μ M cisplatin (+CisPt) (close to their IC_{50}) for 72 h. mRNA levels of ABC drug export pumps were determined by RT-qPCR and expressed as the percentage of mRNA abundance of the housekeeping gene, *RHOT2*. Representative western blots of the selected ABC proteins and α -tubulin were used as a protein loading control in HepG2 (B) and HuH6 (E) cells. Efflux of fluorescent ABC protein substrates: calcein-AM (for MRP1 and MRP2), and carboxyfluorescein diacetate (for MRP3, MRP4 and MRP5) in HepG2 (C) and HuH6 (F) cell lines. Cells were loaded at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 min with these substrates and incubated for another 30 min in the substrate-free medium in the absence (Control) or the presence of inhibitors (probenecid, diclofenac, and fumitremorgin C, respectively). Values are means \pm SEM of 3 independent experiments performed in duplicated wells. *, $p < 0.05$, compared to basal conditions, treated with the vehicle (DMSO); †, $p < 0.05$, comparing with and without inhibitor by paired t -test.

Fig. 6. Effect of long-term incubation with doxorubicin (A) or cisplatin (B) on the viability of HepG2 (A) or HuH6 (B) cells. Cells were either wild-type (WT) or resistant to doxorubicin (DR) or cisplatin (CR), with maintained stimulation due to the presence of the drug in the culture medium (DR+ or CR+) for >10 months and reversibility of chemoresistance following withdrawal of pharmacological pressure for 10 or 28 days (DR- or CR-). Cell viability was determined using the MTT-formazan test after incubating the cells for 72 h with the drugs at the indicated concentrations. Values are expressed as the percentage of viability relative to nontreated cells and represent the mean \pm SEM of at least 3 independent experiments performed in triplicate. *, $p < 0.05$, compared to WT cells by Student's *t*-test for unpaired values.

regulation, which has been associated with enhanced tumor progression [45,46]. However, the modulators of epigenetic targets tested in this study were not able to sensitize resistant cells to chemotherapy.

Despite being able to tolerate high levels of antitumor drugs, the proliferation or invasiveness rates of resistant cell lines were lower than that of the parental cell line, as described by other authors in gemcitabine-resistant cells derived from human CCA [47]. This behavior was not due to the presence of the drug in the culture because it persisted for at least four weeks after withdrawing the pharmacological agent. These results contrast with those from other authors who reported that cisplatin-resistant HB cells were enriched in cancer stem cell-like cells with higher proliferation *in vitro* and tumor growth *in vivo* [48].

Aiming to elucidate which drugs should be avoided and which should be more effective to achieve maximal response with fewer side effects, which is particularly important in pediatric patients [49], persistent chemoresistant HB cells were used to study cross-resistance to

drugs used as second-line treatment for refractory HB or as alternative therapies used in other liver cancers [16]. As expected, chemoresistant cells were also resistant to other members of the same family of drugs used to induce chemoresistance. These were anthracyclines, in the case of doxorubicin, and platinum derivatives, in the case of cisplatin. Besides, specific characteristics of cross-resistance were found. Thus, cisplatin-resistant cells were less sensitive to TKIs (except cabozantinib). This could be due to changes in the expression of resistome genes involved in drug targets and apoptosis activation. On the other hand, doxorubicin-resistant cells showed resistance to drugs that also target topoisomerases, such as irinotecan and etoposide. Although 5-FU and vincristine had different efficacy in the tested HB models, their effect was similar in parental and resistant HB cells. Interestingly, chemoresistant HB cells were still sensitive to cabozantinib, a TKI used to treat adult HCC, but not to the rest of TKIs tested here (sorafenib, regorafenib, and lenvatinib). The fact that chemoresistant HB cells exhibited a slower

Fig. 7. Proliferation, migration, and colony formation in doxorubicin-resistant (HepG2/DR) and wild-type cells (HepG2/WT) HepG2 cells (A) and cisplatin-resistant (HuH6/CR) and wild-type cells (HuH6/WT) HuH6 cells (B). Resistant cells were assayed in the presence (DR+ or CR+) and the absence (DR- or CR-) of maintained drug exposure. Cell density was continuously monitored in real-time using phase holographic imaging. Images of eight regions per well were captured every 60 min for 72 h in two independent experiments performed in duplicate and analyzed with image capture software. The doubling time of the population during steady-state growth rate phase was determined. Results of the wound healing assay illustrate the time course of the wound size performed in the cell culture or its size at different time points. The results are expressed as the percentage of the initial wound area and shown as a representative real-time measurement or mean \pm SEM of at least 15 measurements in five different regions in three independent experiments. Representative images of the clonogenic assay show colonies stained with crystal violet 10 or 15 days after seeding. Quantification of colony forming units (CFU) and average colony area are depicted. Results represent the mean \pm SEM of three independent measurements. *, $p < 0.05$, compared to WT cells by Student's *t*-test. †, $p < 0.05$, comparing DR+ with DR- cells or CR+ with CR- cells by Student's *t*-test.

Fig. 8. Heatmap of the relative qPCR expression levels (RQ) of genes involved in mechanisms of chemoresistance (MOC) by comparing doxorubicin-resistant HepG2 cells (A) or cisplatin-resistant HuH6 cells (B) with their respective parental wild-type cell line. Values are the mean of 9 measurements from 3 separate cultures.

Fig. 9. Immunofluorescence of ABC drug export pumps (green) and the plasma membrane marker Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase (red) in wild-type (HepG2/WT) and doxorubicin-resistant (HepG2/DR) HepG2 cells, and in wild-type (HuH6/WT) and cisplatin-resistant (HuH6/CR) HuH6 cells. Nuclei were counterstained with DAPI. Scale bar: 10 μm.

Table 4
Characterization of resistome in chemoresistant hepatoblastoma cells.

	Gene	Protein	RNA-Seq		qPCR		Proteomics	
			HepG2	HuH6	HepG2	HuH6	HepG2	HuH6
			DR/WT	CR/WT	DR/WT	CR/WT	DR/WT	CR/WT
MOC-1a	<i>SLC22A1</i>	OCT1	2.0	1.5	0.5	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC22A3</i>	OCT3	1.4	N.D.	2.1	N.D.	1.4	1.0
	<i>SLC22A4</i>	OCTN1	1.3	1.3	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC22A5</i>	OCTN2	1.3	1.0	1.5	1.5	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC28A1</i>	CTN1	0.6	20.0	1.0	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC28A2</i>	CTN2	3.0	4.8	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC28A3</i>	CTN3	N.D.	1.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC29A1</i>	ENT1	1.0	0.6	1.4	0.8	0.8	0.5
	<i>SLC29A2</i>	ENT2	1.2	0.4	N.D.	0.3	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLC31A1</i>	CTR1	0.9	1.4	1.4	1.7	0.9	1.0
	<i>SLC47A1</i>	MATE1	0.8	3.5	0.4	N.D.	1.6	1.0
	<i>SLC47A2</i>	MATE2	2.0	2.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLCO1B1</i>	OATP1B1	N.D.	1.3	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLCO1B3</i>	OATP1B3	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SLCO2B1</i>	OATP2B1	3.4	2.9	1.0	3.5	1.1	3.5
	<i>SLCO4A1</i>	OATP4A1	0.6	1.1	0.3	1.5	0.8	0.4
MOC-1b	<i>ABCA8</i>	ABCA8	2.0	2.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>ABCB1</i>	MDR1	14.1	7.2	90.0	N.D.	27.9	0.6
	<i>ABCC1</i>	MRP1	1.0	0.9	1.9	0.9	1.5	0.6
	<i>ABCC2</i>	MRP2	0.7	2.7	1.9	3.0	1.1	1.2
	<i>ABCC3</i>	MRP3	1.0	5.2	3.6	N.D.	1.2	0.6
	<i>ABCC4</i>	MRP4	1.0	0.6	1.0	2.5	1.4	0.5
	<i>ABCC5</i>	MRP5	1.0	1.7	1.5	2.3	1.0	0.9
	<i>ABCC6</i>	MRP6	1.4	N.D.	1.3	3.0	1.2	1.0
	<i>ABCC10</i>	MRP7	0.7	2.0	1.3	2.0	1.6	1.2
	<i>ABCG2</i>	BCRP	1.3	0.3	0.6	0.4	2.1	0.1
	<i>MVP</i>	MVP	1.8	1.3	0.9	2.0	N.D.	N.D.
	MOC-2	<i>CES1</i>	EST1	0.7	2.8	0.3	2.6	0.6
<i>CES2</i>		EST2	1.2	1.8	0.6	1.5	0.9	2.6
<i>CYP1A1</i>		CP1A1	0.4	1.6	2.0	5.0	0.9	0.2
<i>CYP1A2</i>		CP1A2	N.D.	13.5	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>CYP3A4</i>		CP3A4	4.0	2.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>DPYD</i>		DHPDHase	0.6	1.0	1.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>GSTA1</i>		GSTA1	0.7	2.2	5.0	1.5	0.5	1.6
<i>GSTP1</i>		GSTP1	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.3	0.9	1.1
<i>TYMP</i>		TP	1.8	1.5	11.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>UGT1A</i>		UD11	1.8	4.0	4.0	2.0	1.3	1.0
<i>UPP1</i>		UPP1	1.5	0.8	7.7	1.3	0.6	0.6
<i>UMPS</i>		UMPS	1.1	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.0	1.2
MOC-3		<i>EGFR</i>	EGFR	1.9	1.7	2.2	3.0	1.3
	<i>ESR2</i>	ER-β	2.0	1.2	N.D.	0.2	N.D.	N.D.

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

	<i>KDR</i>	VEGFR-2	N.D.	2.0	N.D.	2.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>KIT</i>	CD117	N.D.	0.3	N.D.	0.8	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>MTOR</i>	MTOR	1.1	1.0	2.2	1.1	1.0	1.3
	<i>PDGFRA</i>	PDGFR α	1.0	0.4	N.D.	0.3	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>TOP1</i>	TOP1	1.2	0.9	1.8	0.9	0.8	1.0
	<i>TOP2A</i>	TOP2A	0.6	2.4	0.2	3.1	0.9	2.0
	<i>TYMS</i>	TS	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	N.D.	N.D.
MOC-4	<i>DHFR</i>	DYR	1.0	1.2	N.D.	0.0	0.9	2.8
	<i>ERCC1</i>	ERCC1	0.9	1.1	2.4	2.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>MLH1</i>	MLH1	1.0	1.6	5.5	1.7	1.0	1.0
	<i>MLH3</i>	MLH3	1.1	1.4	2.0	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>MSH2</i>	MSH2	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.9	2.1	1.4
	<i>MSH6</i>	MSH6	1.1	0.9	1.2	1.0	1.1	1.5
	<i>PMS1</i>	PMS1	1.1	1.1	2.6	0.9	0.6	0.4
	<i>PMS2</i>	PMS2	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.7	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>TCEA2</i>	TCEA2	1.2	3.0	0.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>UNG</i>	UNG	1.1	0.8	0.6	0.8	1.7	0.8
	<i>XPA</i>	XPA	1.2	1.8	2.2	2.0	N.D.	N.D.
MOC-5a	<i>BAX</i>	BAX	0.9	1.0	2.0	1.1	0.8	2.8
	<i>BCL2L1</i>	B2CL1	0.8	1.5	2.3	1.6	1.4	2.7
	<i>CDKN1A</i>	p21	2.6	1.4	4.1	5.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>DIABLO</i>	DBLOH	1.1	1.1	2.3	1.4	3.7	1.5
	<i>FAS</i>	TNR6	1.7	2.0	4.9	N.D.	1.1	1.0
	<i>PSMD9</i>	PSMD9	1.6	1.0	4.3	1.1	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>PTEN</i>	PTEN	1.2	0.9	0.0	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>TNFRSF10A</i>	TRAIL-R1	1.0	N.D.	2.4	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>TNFRSF10B</i>	TRAIL-R2	1.1	1.1	2.1	1.5	N.D.	N.D.
MOC-5b	<i>AKT1</i>	AKT1	1.0	1.2	0.9	0.9	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>BCL2</i>	Bcl-2	2.6	0.2	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>BIRC2</i>	C-IAP1	1.0	1.4	4.9	1.4	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>BIRC3</i>	C-IAP2	1.3	2.1	3.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>BIRC5</i>	Survivin	0.7	0.9	0.3	0.8	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>BIRC7</i>	KIAP	3.7	2.0	N.D.	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>CFLAR</i>	c-FLIP	1.3	1.8	2.2	2.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>KRT13</i>	K1C13	N.D.	2.0	N.D.	N.D.	7.6	0.4
	<i>MTDH</i>	Metadherin	1.0	0.8	3.5	0.6	0.7	1.2
	<i>MYC</i>	c-Myc	0.9	0.9	1.7	0.8	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>NAIP</i>	NAIP	1.3	2.7	3.0	1.5	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>NFKB1</i>	EBP-1	0.9	0.7	1.2	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>PIK3CG</i>	PI3K- γ	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>RPL6</i>	RL6	1.3	0.7	3.0	0.8	0.9	0.7
	<i>XIAP</i>	ILP	1.3	1.1	0.9	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>YAP1</i>	YAP1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	N.D.	N.D.
MOC-6	<i>NANOG</i>	NANOG	N.D.	8.0	1.0	1.0	N.D.	N.D.
MOC-7	<i>ALDH1A1</i>	AL1A1	1.1	2.8	2.5	1.9	0.9	3.6
	<i>CD44</i>	CD44	3.0	2.2	1.0	3.5	1.0	11.5
	<i>NFE2L2</i>	Nrf-2	0.8	1.1	1.9	1.2	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>NOTCH3</i>	NOTC3	0.9	0.9	N.D.	1.2	1.0	0.9
	<i>POU5F1B</i>	Oct4-pg1	N.D.	1.5	N.D.	0.8	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>PROM1</i>	PROM1	1.8	1.3	8.8	1.3	2.3	1.0
	<i>SOX2</i>	SOX-2	5.0	2.0	7.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>SOX9</i>	SOX-9	1.0	0.9	0.7	0.9	N.D.	N.D.
	<i>TGFB1</i>	TGF- β 1	0.9	6.7	2.2	5.0	N.D.	N.D.

Expression fold-change of genes involved in mechanisms of chemoresistance (MOC) in doxorubicin-resistant (DR) HepG2 cells and cisplatin-resistant (CR) Huh6 cells as compared with their respective parental cell line (wild-type, WT). The expression levels were determined by RNA-Seq. RT-qPCR using microfluidic cards or TLDA. and high-throughput proteomics. N.D., not detected. The red background indicates fold-change values ≥ 2 (moderate), ≥ 5 (high), or ≥ 10 (very high). The blue background indicates decreased expression with fold-change expression levels of ≤ 0.5 .

Table 5

Changes in the expression of genes involved in epigenetics, classified as erasers, readers, scaffolds, and writers in resistant hepatoblastoma cells, determined by RNA-Seq.

	HepG2			HuH6		
	WT	DR	Fold-change	WT	CR	Fold-change
Erasers						
<i>HDAC9</i>	0.08	0.77 ^a	10.3	0.20	0.49	2.5
<i>HR</i>	11.4	4.2 ^a	0.4	0.08	2.7 ^a	33.5
<i>PADI2</i>	0.01	0.03	2.7	0.54	58.7 ^a	109
<i>USP44</i>	0.36	0.37	1.0	1.2	0.40 ^a	0.3
<i>UTY</i>	> 0.01	0.19 ^a	1860	13.1	20.1	1.5
Readers						
<i>CHD5</i>	0.46	2.3 ^a	5.0	0.94	2.7	2.9
<i>MLL3</i>	11.2	7.5	0.7	104.0	24.5 ^a	0.2
<i>PAX6</i>	1.0	8.6 ^a	8.4	0.68	0.79	1.2
<i>PDP1</i>	3.8	9.8	2.6	61.9	25.7 ^a	0.4
<i>PHF19</i>	34	20	0.6	10.8	73.1 ^a	6.8
<i>SFMBT2</i>	0.05	0.34 ^a	6.6	6.5	9.4	1.4
Scaffolds						
<i>EID1</i>	0.01	0.41 ^a	40.8	35.9	44.5	1.2
<i>NAP1L2</i>	0.06	0.31	4.8	0.09	2.0 ^a	21.1
<i>SNAI2</i>	0.35	1.15	3.3	0.01	0.26 ^a	24.0
Writers						
<i>MECOM</i>	0.09	0.43 ^a	4.7	14.7	14.9	1.0
<i>PARP10</i>	33.9	41.8	1.2	1.2	14.9 ^a	12.9
<i>PRDM6</i>	0.02	0.16 ^a	8.4	3.7	3.4	0.9
<i>PRDM7</i>	0.04	1.04 ^a	25.3	0.04	0.57 ^a	16.4
<i>PRDM8</i>	0.05	0.27 ^a	5.9	0.056	0.013	0.2
<i>RAG1</i>	0.06	0.33 ^a	5.5	1.6	3.2	2.1
<i>SETD7</i>	1.9	17.8 ^a	9.3	38	72	1.9

The expression levels (FPKM) were determined in three different cultures of HepG2 cells resistant to doxorubicin (HepG2/DR) and HuH6 cells resistant to cisplatin (HuH6/CR), as well as their corresponding wild-type (WT) cells using RNA-Seq. Only genes with considerable expression levels (> 0.1) and significant differences (> 2 fold) compared to parental wild-type (WT) cells are depicted. ^a, $p < 0.05$ as compared with WT cells.

proliferation rate suggests that cabozantinib's mechanism of action extends beyond proliferation inhibition but may involve alternative vulnerabilities in resistant cells. Indeed, cabozantinib is the only of the assayed TKIs that targets c-MET [50]. Notably, c-MET is commonly overexpressed in HB and has been implicated in the activation of pro-survival pathways [51]. Our RNA-Seq analysis confirmed high MET expression in both parental HepG2 and HuH6 cells, with no significant changes in resistant cells. Accordingly, c-MET inhibition by cabozantinib may account for the sensitivity of resistant cells to this drug, although other contributing factors cannot be excluded. This finding is highly relevant, from a clinical perspective, because it recommends further investigation aimed at using cabozantinib as a therapeutic option for chemoresistant HB tumors.

In conclusion, drug export pumps, but not SLC uptake transporters, play an important role in the lack of response of HB to conventional chemotherapy. Moreover, cabozantinib emerges as a potential alternative anticancer drug to be used in non-responding patients.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

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Fig. 10. Effect of drugs used to treat hepatoblastoma on the viability of wild-type (WT) and doxorubicin-resistant (DR) HepG2 cells (A) and cisplatin-resistant (CR) HuH6 cells (B). The impact of epigenetic modulators (CM272 and PFI-2) on the toxic effect of doxorubicin in HepG2 (A) and HuH6 (B) cells was assayed. Cell viability was determined using the MTT-formazan test after incubating the cells with the drugs for 72 h. In experiments with epigenetic modulators, these drugs were added to the culture 72 h before adding doxorubicin or cisplatin. Values are expressed as the percentage of viability in non-treated cells. They are shown as mean \pm SEM of 4–6 independent experiments performed in triplicate wells. *, $p < 0.05$, comparing WT with chemoresistant cells by Student's *t*-test. No difference ($p > 0.05$) between values with and without epigenetic modulators was found.

Table 6

Cytostatic effect of antitumor drugs used in first- and second-line treatment of hepatoblastoma in wild-type (WT) HuH6 and HepG2 cells and after long-term exposure to cisplatin (CR) or doxorubicin (DR).

	IC ₅₀		RQ	IC ₅₀		RQ
	HepG2 WT	HepG2/ DR		HuH6 WT	HuH6/ CR	
Anthracyclines						
(μM)						
Doxorubicin	0.17 \pm 0.02	8.7 \pm 2.3 ^a	51.1	0.08 \pm 0.02	0.12 \pm 0.02	1.6
Epirubicin	0.3 \pm 0.0	9.3 \pm 0.8 ^a	31.0	0.04 \pm 0.01	0.05 \pm 0.00	1.3
Idarubicin	0.06 \pm 0.02	0.65 \pm 0.24 ^a	10.2	0.04 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.01 ^a	2.0
Platinum						
derivatives (μM)						
Cisplatin	7.7 \pm 0.9	20.6 \pm 2.4 ^a	2.7	8.6 \pm 0.6	31.3 \pm 1.3 ^a	3.7
Oxaliplatin	4.8 \pm 1.5	6.8 \pm 1.7	1.4	1.7 \pm 0.5	7.9 \pm 3.2	4.8
Nitrogen-base						
analogs (μM)						
5-Fluorouracil	>50	>50	1.0	9.1 \pm 0.9	9.2 \pm 1.3	1.0
Camptothecins						
(μM)						
Irinotecan	2.7 \pm 0.6	9.9 \pm 0.1 ^a	3.7	17.6 \pm 2.6	20.7 \pm 3.2	1.2
Podophylotoxins						
(μM)						
Etoposide	9.3 \pm 2.5	> 40 ^a	4.0	4.7 \pm 1.8	14.4 \pm 3.5 ^a	3.0
Vinca alkaloids						
(nM)						
Vinblastine	>25,000	>25,000	1.0	0.7 \pm 0.1	2.2 \pm 0.3 ^a	3.2
Vincristine	>20,000	>20,000	1.0	0.6 \pm 0.2	0.6 \pm 0.3	1.0
Tyrosine kinase						
inhibitors (μM)						
Cabozantinib	5.2 \pm 2.3	5.7 \pm 1.4	1.1	6.0 \pm 0.4	8.6 \pm 1.4	1.4
Lenvatinib	> 20	> 20	1.0	0.5 \pm 0.0	> 10 ^a 20	>
Regorafenib	2.0 \pm 0.2	2.5 \pm 0.7	1.2	1.3 \pm 0.2	6.7 \pm 1.2 ^a	5.3
Sorafenib	4.6 \pm 0.6	4.2 \pm 0.5	0.9	1.5 \pm 0.2	3.9 \pm 0.1 ^a	2.7

The half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) was calculated after incubating the cells with increasing concentrations of the drugs for 72 h and determining cell viability by MTT-formazan assay. Values are means \pm SEM of at least 3 independent experiments performed in triplicate wells. RQ, relative sensitivity to drugs compared to that of WT cells. ^a, $p < 0.05$, compared to WT cells by Student's *t*-test.

editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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